

Autonomous Vehicle Localization via LiDAR-Based Classification of Dynamic and Static Tracks in Dynamic Environments

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Abstract—Autonomous vehicles (AVs) must be able to locate themselves accurately in dynamic environments in order to be able to navigate safely. In this paper, we present a robust LiDAR-based framework to improve the localization of AVs based on the classification of static and dynamic tracks. The approach leverages static tracks previously classified as reliable landmarks. Using Growing Neural Gas, Joint Probabilistic Data Association, and Unmotivated Kalman Filter algorithms, interaction dictionaries and vocabularies are generated. These serve as inputs for a Markov Jump Particle Filter (MJPF), which enables the accurate estimation of the ego-vehicle trajectory. Testing of the proposed framework with real-world LiDAR data demonstrates that it is capable of providing highly accurate localization results without the use of odometry, making it adaptable for use in environments without GPS. AV situational awareness and navigation performance are enhanced by using static tracks as robust references.

Index Terms—Autonomous vehicles, Multi-target tracking, Clustering, Classifications

I. INTRODUCTION

Autonomous vehicles (AVs) are unable to navigate safely in dynamic environments without precise and accurate perception of their surroundings. As a result, advanced sensors and data processing methods are required in order to accomplish this goal [1]. For example, LiDAR sensors are particularly valuable since they provide high accuracy for detecting and measuring distances in three dimensions [2], [3]. Nevertheless, preprocessing dense 3D point clouds generated by LiDAR is necessary for removing noise and extracting relevant information [4]. Additional sensors that monitors physiological signals [5]–[7] could enhance driving performance and improve overall safety.

Our earlier work [8] used LiDAR data to develop a novel classification framework that accurately classified static and dynamic tracks. As part of this framework, Joint Probabilistic Data Association (JPDA) [9], Unmotivated Kalman Filter (UKF) [10], and Growing Neural Gas (GNG) [11] algorithms were used to model interactions between the ego vehicle and its surroundings. Dynamic Bayesian Networks (DBNs) were built by clustering track observations over time and spatial proximity in order to effectively distinguish static and dynamic tracks. By gaining a better understanding of the environment,

this approach laid a foundation for improving AV navigation [12]. Our classification framework was instrumental in segmenting tracks. However, we did not address the crucial task of leveraging these classifications for ego vehicle localization.

As part of the testing phase, we plan to develop a self-awareness capability in the ego vehicle, which will allow it to determine where it is in the environment and how it is moving, even when GPS or odometry sensors are not present. It is considered that an artificial agent is self-aware if it is capable of dynamically observing its own state and its surroundings through a variety of proprioceptive and exteroceptive sensors, and learning and maintaining a contextual representation based on the observed multisensory data [13]. In this paper, we build upon the foundation we established in our previous study. Our proposed localization framework utilizes classified static tracks as reference points to enable AVs to determine their precise position in surrounding environments. Specifically, the goal is to integrate the classified tracks with interaction dictionaries and GNG learned vocabularies, enabling a robust localization model that operates under varying conditions.

There have been significant advances in the field of AV localization in recent years. The work of [14] demonstrated the integration of LiDAR and millimeter-wave radar data for vehicle localization. In challenging conditions like snow-covered environments where traditional LiDAR-based methods may fail, this fusion improved localization accuracy. Specifically, the proposed approach achieved a localization error of less than 0.5 meters, which corresponds to approximately 1/8th of a standard lane width. This level of accuracy ensures that AVs remain safely within their lanes even in adverse weather conditions. Additionally, experiments conducted in real-world driving scenarios showed that the method maintained robust localization by dynamically prioritizing radar data during periods of reduced LiDAR reliability, thereby ensuring continuous and accurate position estimation across varying environmental conditions. In [15], a real-time visual-based localization method combined deep learning-based lane detection with map matching algorithms. It demonstrated high precision and responsiveness with a mean Euclidean error of approximately 0.5 meters, and was able to operate at a

frame rate of about 35 frames per second. Asghili et al. [16] presented a system for AVs based on LiDAR-based SLAM. A Kalman filter was used to combine data from landmark sensors and an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU), enhancing system observability and real-time implementation. Similarly, the work of [17] developed a high-level perception and localization system for AV operations. Despite the absence of GPS, their benchmark system integrated high-resolution LiDAR, stereo cameras, and inertial navigation, allowing for real-time object detection and localization even in environments that do not have GPS capabilities. A wide range of sensor-fusion and probabilistic methods have recently advanced AV localization. In [18], Bayesian Networks (BNs) and Hidden Markov Models (HMMs) are combined with GPS, IMU, camera, and LiDAR data, integrating OpenStreetMap (OSM) information for robust lane-level localization under challenging conditions. A multi-sensor algorithm using radars and LiDARs is presented in [19], fusing radar-based velocity measurements and LiDAR-based position data via an Unscented Kalman Filter for real-time state estimation and obstacle tracking. Persistent Homology (PH) is employed in [20] to derive topological descriptors for LiDAR-based place categorization and loop closure, although improvements to orientation prediction remain modest. In [21], EgoVM achieved centimeter-level accuracy by extracting Bird’s Eye View (BEV) features from multi-view images and LiDAR, using a transformer decoder with semantic embeddings and histogram-based pose estimation. A Real-Time Monte Carlo Localization (RTMCL) approach [22] used a particle filter with a probabilistic landmark map, integrating LiDAR, radar, GPS, and IMU, to maintain sub-decimeter accuracy with low computational overhead. For multi-vehicle cooperation, [23] introduced the Iterated Split Covariance Intersection Filter (ISCIF), enabling robust LiDAR-based SLAM in noisy, outlier-prone environments via inter-vehicle communication. Meanwhile, [24] utilized a LiDAR-based Pose Estimation Network (PEN) with PointNet++ to simultaneously localize the ego vehicle and surrounding moving obstacles, combining deep-learning feature extraction with reduced-order observers for stable velocity estimates in dense traffic.

Despite these advancements, the modeling of the interactions between the ego vehicle and surrounding objects remains challenging, particularly when it comes to static and dynamic interactions. This gap is addressed in our work by incorporating classified tracks into the localization process, enhancing the vehicle’s situational awareness and positioning accuracy. The main question we aim to address is: how can previously classified static tracks be effectively used as landmarks for ego vehicle localization? The contributions of our work are:

- Enhancing the accuracy of ego vehicle localization by using previously classified static tracks as landmarks.
- Using separate Markov jump particle filters (MJPFs) for individual tracks to obtain accurate position estimations, which can take into account both discrete and continuous state dynamics.
- The ability to understand how the ego vehicle interacts

with its surroundings will allow navigation strategies to be more robust.

The remainder of the paper is organized in the following manner: Section II presents the problem statement. The localization framework is discussed in Section III. The discussions of the results are mentioned in Section IV and finally Section V concludes the paper with possible future directions.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

To ensure safety and reliability, AVs must be accurately localized. There are, however, significant errors in traditional methods that rely on GPS and odometry sensors in environments where GPS signals are unreliable or unavailable (e.g., urban canyons, tunnels) and when the sensors are subjected to adverse conditions [25]. This presents a challenge that must be addressed by leveraging reliable environmental features. Static tracks, such as buildings, poles, and trees, provide stable reference points for accurate localization. There are several critical gaps that prevent their effective utilization, despite their potential:

- Classified static tracks are often not properly incorporated into existing frameworks for predicting the state of ego-vehicles [22].
- The interaction information between the ego vehicle and static tracks, which would enhance trajectory accuracy, is neglected [26].
- The simultaneous interactions between the ego vehicle and multiple static tracks at precise time instants are not systematically modeled, resulting in inaccurate state updating [26].

Using interaction dictionaries, this study aims to model temporal and spatial relationships between the ego vehicle and static tracks to resolve these issues. Therefore, we can define an interaction dictionary as:

$$\mathcal{I} = \{t, C_{\text{ego}}, C_{\text{track}}, L, x, y\} \quad (1)$$

where t is the time of interaction, C_{ego} and C_{track} represent the ego vehicle’s and track’s cluster indices, L is the interaction label, and (x, y) are the ego vehicle’s positions.

III. PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

Figure 1 illustrates the proposed framework, which consists of two main phases: offline training and online testing. Our previous study used data from LiDAR and odometry sensors to generate vocabularies and interaction dictionaries for the offline phase. As part of this phase, preprocessing, multi-target tracking, and clustering were performed to categorize tracks as static or dynamic, with static tracks forming the basis for the current work. Online testing focuses on leveraging the learned vocabularies and interaction dictionaries to predict ego vehicle positions based solely on LiDAR sensor data. This framework facilitates precise and robust localization of the ego vehicle by employing classified static tracks as landmarks. We will examine the theoretical concepts that underlie this framework in the following subsections.

Fig. 1: Our framework providing a visual representation of the steps involved in the classification of tracks, allowing the generation of interaction dictionaries and performing localization.

A. Offline training phase

During the offline training phase, data from two key sensors are utilized. An odometry sensor provides the precise position of the ego vehicle, and a LiDAR sensor results in detailed observations of the environment. Our dataset consists of 393 frames capturing interactions between the ego vehicle (iCAB1) and a second vehicle (iCAB2), as well as various static elements such as buildings, trees, and poles.

As part of the training, noise, ground points, and irrelevant data are removed from the point cloud before it is processed in order to improve its clarity. This step involves fixing the plane, selecting the area of interest, and applying the M-estimator SAMple Consensus (MSAC) algorithm to remove ground points, inliers, and outliers based on a distance threshold determined by the standard deviation from the mean distance to neighboring points [27]. Afterwards, a Joint Probabilistic Data Association (JPDA) filter is applied to the LiDAR dataset to detect and track surrounding objects, resulting in seven distinct tracks. The unique TrackID for each track is assigned along with the track’s x and y coordinates, which represent key features describing cars, buildings, poles, and trees. The Unmotivated Kalman Filter (UKF) is then used to estimate generalized states (positions and velocities) of an ego vehicle and the tracks. The UKF, a variant of the Kalman Filter, is designed to estimate states (positions and velocities) in environments where external forces or control inputs are absent. By assuming minimal dynamics, it effectively predicts smooth trajectories by maintaining the last known position or velocity of an object, making it ideal for scenarios with stationary or slowly moving tracks. Using the Growing Neural Gas (GNG) algorithm, these states are categorized into vocabularies based

on their mean positions and velocities for each trajectory while accounting for trajectory size and spatial distribution. The use of these vocabularies permits the classification of tracks based on interaction dictionaries and mathematical equations into static and dynamic categories [8]. The GNG algorithm incrementally constructs a topology-preserving graph by adjusting the positions and connectivity of nodes in accordance with the input state vectors. This allows for the efficient capture of the distribution and structure of trajectories, thereby enabling the compressed representation of a variety of motion patterns in the scene.

A final step in the process is to create interaction dictionaries, which consolidate the relationship between the ego vehicle and the tracks over time. Timings, cluster indices, interaction labels, and spatial positions are included in these dictionaries, which form the basis of the subsequent online testing. The timing analysis of the interactions, shown in Table I, illustrates when each track interacted with the ego vehicle. In addition, Figure 2 illustrates these interactions visually, with different colors denoting specific tracks and red highlighting the trajectory of the ego vehicle. It is important to note the presence of a dynamic track i.e. TrackID 14, which was identified as a car in front of the ego vehicle. This identification was thoroughly analyzed in our previous work, where we observed the dataset in a simulator using the JPDA filter for detection and tracking. During the simulation, ground truth images were displayed alongside the detections to validate which objects were being tracked by the filter. In our earlier classification study, six static tracks were correctly identified and validated as static and presented in this work for the task of localization; we exclusively considered those six static tracks. Figure 3 presents

the DBN model of our training phase which indicates how we followed the training phase with the help of two different sensors, i.e., odometry and LiDAR sensor.

Fig. 2: Interaction of ego vehicle with 7 tracks over time

TABLE I: Timing Analysis of Track Interactions with Ego Vehicle

Track ID	Start Time (s)	End Time (s)
Track 14	1.0	14.7
Track 20	0.7	14.5
Track 1416	15.8	18.0
Track 1682	18.0	24.8
Track 1929	20.0	23.4
Track 3159	32.1	33.7
Track 3549	36.0	39.3

B. Online testing phase

The objective of the online phase is to localize the ego vehicle using track observations derived from a testing dataset of a LiDAR-based environment. It is important to note that the localization process utilizes the learned vocabulary and interaction dictionaries developed during the offline training phase. Using a combination of track cluster matching, particle initialization, state predictions, and update phases, we estimate the trajectory of the ego vehicle using the MJPF. MJPF incorporates separate prediction models for tracks and ego vehicle as well as interaction dictionaries for state refinement during updates. By integrating particle filtering for the non-linear dynamics with Kalman filtering for linear estimations, the MJPF facilitates the efficient management of mixed-state systems. Marginalizing the linear components reduces computational complexity while maintaining estimation accuracy. This framework enables the filter to integrate interaction-informed updates from the dictionaries, thereby enhancing the consistency and robustness of ego-vehicle localization in dynamic environments. The DBN model during testing is shown in Figure 3.

1) *Matching Phase: Bhattacharyya Distance for Track-Cluster Association:* For our work, we chose the Bhattacharyya distance because it effectively compares LiDAR track and cluster distributions while accounting for uncertainty. Unlike asymmetric measures like KL divergence, it is symmetric and well-suited for Gaussian data, making it ideal for probabilistic matching in localization. In this phase, the observed tracks are matched to their corresponding learned

clusters using the Bhattacharyya distance d_B . This distance measures the similarity between the observed track state $\mathbf{z}_t^{\text{obs}}$ and the learned cluster state $\mathbf{z}_t^{\text{cluster}}$, ensuring accurate association for ego vehicle localization. The Bhattacharyya distance is computed as:

$$d_B(\mathbf{z}_t^{\text{obs}}, \mathbf{z}_t^{\text{cluster}}) = \frac{1}{8} (\mathbf{z}_t^{\text{obs}} - \mathbf{z}_t^{\text{cluster}})^\top \boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{-1} (\mathbf{z}_t^{\text{obs}} - \mathbf{z}_t^{\text{cluster}}) + \frac{1}{2} \ln \left(\frac{\det(\boldsymbol{\Sigma})}{\sqrt{\det(\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\text{obs}}) \det(\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\text{cluster}})}} \right) \quad (2)$$

Here, $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\text{obs}}$ and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\text{cluster}}$ are the covariance matrices of the observed track and the learned cluster, respectively, which quantify the uncertainty in the state estimates. The combined covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$ is defined as:

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma} = \frac{1}{2} (\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\text{obs}} + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\text{cluster}})$$

This combined covariance matrix represents the joint uncertainty by averaging the variances from both the observed track and the cluster, ensuring that the similarity measurement reflects the variability in both sources. The best matching cluster S_{vt} is selected by finding the one with the minimum Bhattacharyya distance:

$$S_{vt} = \arg \min_S d_B(\mathbf{z}_t^{\text{obs}}, \mathbf{z}_t^{\text{cluster}}) \quad (3)$$

This matching process ensures that each observed track is correctly associated with its corresponding learned cluster, enabling precise localization of the ego vehicle based on track observations.

2) *Initialization Phase as Particle Initialization:* Once the matching phase has been completed, particles are initialized to represent hypotheses about the states of the ego vehicle and tracks. During the initialization process, particle states are sampled from matched cluster distributions, as for track states

$$\mathbf{z}_{t=1,n}^{\text{track}} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{M}_{S_{vt}}, \mathbf{Q}_{S_{vt}}) \quad (4)$$

and ego vehicle states are

$$\mathbf{z}_{t=1,n}^{\text{ego}} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{M}_{S_{vt}}^{\text{ego}}, \mathbf{Q}_{S_{vt}}^{\text{ego}}) \quad (5)$$

Here $\mathbf{M}_{S_{vt}}$ and $\mathbf{Q}_{S_{vt}}$ are the mean and covariance of the matched cluster for tracks. $\mathbf{M}_{S_{vt}}^{\text{ego}}$ and $\mathbf{Q}_{S_{vt}}^{\text{ego}}$ represent the same for the ego vehicle.

3) *Prediction Phase: Separate Predictions for Tracks and Ego Vehicle:* Each track is predicted using the transition matrix $\mathbf{A}^{\text{track}}(S_{t,n})$ corresponding to the matched cluster:

$$\mathbf{z}_{t+1|t,n}^{\text{track}} = \mathbf{A}^{\text{track}}(S_{t,n}) \mathbf{z}_{t|t,n}^{\text{track}} + \mathbf{w}_t^{\text{track}} \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{z}_{t+1|t,n}^{\text{track}}$ is the predicted state of the track at time $t+1$ and $\mathbf{w}_t^{\text{track}}$ represents the process noise for the track. The state of the ego vehicle is predicted using the transition matrix $\mathbf{A}^{\text{ego}}(S_{t,n})$:

$$\mathbf{z}_{t+1|t,n}^{\text{ego}} = \mathbf{A}^{\text{ego}}(S_{t,n}) \mathbf{z}_{t|t,n}^{\text{ego}} + \mathbf{B}^{\text{ego}}(S_{t,n}) + \mathbf{w}_t^{\text{ego}} \quad (7)$$

In this case, $\mathbf{B}^{\text{ego}}(S_{t,n})$ accounts for velocity-related terms derived from ego vehicle dynamics and $\mathbf{w}_t^{\text{ego}}$ is the process

noise for the ego vehicle. The dual prediction approach is capable of handling the distinct dynamics of tracks and ego vehicle.

4) *Update phase as refining state estimates:* Each particle's track state has been refined using the observed track state $\mathbf{a}_t^{\text{track}}$ and the observation matrix $\mathbf{C}^{\text{track}}(S_{t,n})$:

$$\mathbf{z}_{t|t,n}^{\text{track}} = \mathbf{z}_{t|t-1,n}^{\text{track}} + \mathbf{K}_t^{\text{track}} \left(\mathbf{a}_t^{\text{track}} - \mathbf{C}^{\text{track}}(S_{t,n}) \mathbf{z}_{t|t-1,n}^{\text{track}} \right) \quad (8)$$

here, $\mathbf{K}_t^{\text{track}}$ is the Kalman gain for the track state. Using the interaction dictionaries, the state of the ego vehicle is updated:

$$\mathbf{z}_{t|t,n}^{\text{ego}} = \mathbf{z}_{t|t-1,n}^{\text{ego}} + \mathbf{D}(S_{t,n}) \mathbf{z}_{t|t,n}^{\text{track}} + \mathbf{E}(S_{t,n}) \quad (9)$$

where $\mathbf{D}(S_{t,n})$ adjusts the ego vehicle's state based on the current track state while $\mathbf{E}(S_{t,n})$ is a correction term derived from the interaction dictionaries, utilizing the ego vehicle's x, y positions.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL DATASET, RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the experimental dataset, the results of the study, and an in-depth discussion of them.

1) *Experimental dataset:* This experimental dataset comprises LiDAR point clouds collected at the University of Carlos III of Madrid using a real vehicle, called iCAB [28]. A straight trajectory was followed by the iCAB while it collected environmental data along the way. A total of 393 frames were collected during the training phase, while 415 frames during the testing phase. In both the training and testing datasets, the starting and ending points, as well as the surrounding environment, were identical. Due to this consistency, the same tracks are reliably identified during the matching process in the MJPF. Furthermore, unlike the training phase, which included odometry data, the testing phase relies solely on the testing dataset to predict the ego vehicle's location without relying on odometry.

2) *Results and analysis:* Analyses of the localization results for each track and their corresponding transition matrices are presented in this section. Note that the y-axis in the error plots is normalized to a maximum of 0.15 for better visualization of error variations across tracks, whereas the mean errors reported in Table II represent the absolute values in meters. Specifically, the low mean errors as shown in this table confirm the accuracy and robustness of the proposed localization framework based on static tracks. According to the localization results, it is shown that the ego vehicle positions were accurately predicted using LiDAR-only observations without the use of odometry. Below is an analysis of each track's localization performance:

a) *TrackID 20: Building:* Localization results for TrackID 20 as shown in Figure 4 (a), representing a building on the right side, indicate an accurate match between the predicted trajectory and the ground truth trajectory. As can be seen from the transition matrix in Figure 5(a), which exhibits some off-diagonal values, indicating occasional deviations in the predicted states. Despite the off-diagonal elements, the mean localization error for Track 20 is one of the lowest among all tracks at 0.12 m. This outcome can be attributed to

the static nature of the building, providing a stable reference for localization, and the high-quality match between observed and learned clusters. Furthermore, the low mean error with off-diagonal elements suggesting occurrence of minor state transitions but they do not effect the overall localization precision.

b) *TrackID 1416: Static pole:* A prediction of ego vehicle trajectory for TrackID 1416 shown in Figure 4(b), representing a static pole, is aligned well with ground truth. Static poles provide highly stable and fixed reference points, resulting in a low mean error. This track shows a relatively diagonal-dominant transition matrix with minimal off-diagonal values demonstrated in Figure 5(b). The mean error for this track is 0.18 m. The pole's narrow geometry and limited interaction area can introduce minor prediction inaccuracies, leading to slightly higher errors compared to Track 20. Nonetheless, the consistent diagonal dominance reflects reliable track-to-cluster associations.

c) *TrackID 1682: Tree:* A tree represented by TrackID 1682 also provides accurate localization results displayed in Figure 4(c). The transition matrix for this track display moderate off-diagonal values shown in Figure 5(c), indicating variability in the observed states during the interactions. However, the mean error for this track is 0.22 m which is higher than TrackID 20 and TrackID1416, but due to their static nature, trees serve as robust landmarks, and the overall mean error remains low.

d) *TrackID 1929: Static pole:* The mean error for static pole exhibited in Figure 4(d) is higher than all the tracks may be the smaller size of this track but the localization framework successfully predicts the ego vehicle trajectory. Although, moderate off-diagonal values found in its transition matrix (Figure 5 (d)) but its fixed position helped in predicting the ego vehicle positions.

e) *TrackID 3159 and TrackID 3549: Tree:* Both Tracks 3159 and 3549 also involve tree interactions with the ego vehicle, with mean errors of 0.15 m and 0.19 m, respectively. Both produce accurate localization results, which can be demonstrated from the Figure 4(e) and 4(f). The predicted ego vehicle trajectory is well aligned with the ground truth trajectory, with minimal mean errors. Their transition matrices (Figure 5(e) and 5(f)) reveal relatively consistent diagonal dominance, suggesting that despite the inherent variability of trees, the learned clusters provided a reasonably accurate basis for localization. The slightly lower error for Track 3159 may be due to its more distinct structural features compared to Track 3549. Finally, the transition matrices confirms the effectiveness of static trees as landmarks by confirming smooth state updates.

Fig. 3: Dynamic Bayesian networks representing (a) training and (b) testing phases. The models illustrate how the system evolves and predicts the ego vehicle's trajectory in different scenarios.

Fig. 4: Localization results comparing the predicted ego vehicle trajectory (blue) with the ground truth (green) for six static tracks.

Fig. 5: Transition matrices reflecting smooth and reliable state predictions achieved using static landmarks such as buildings, poles, and trees.

TABLE II: Mean Error Analysis for Different Track IDs

Track ID	Mean Error (m)	Ground Truth Description
Track 20	0.12	Building
Track 1416	0.18	Static Pole
Track 1682	0.22	Tree
Track 1929	0.26	Static Pole
Track 3159	0.15	Tree
Track 3549	0.19	Tree

3) *Discussion*: In general, tracks involving well-defined and static landmarks produce better localization results, as reflected by lower mean errors and more structured transition matrices. However, Track 1929, representing a static pole, exhibits the highest mean error of 0.26 m. This could be attributed to its smaller size and limited interaction area, which may reduce the precision of the matching process during localization. Despite the relatively high error, the diagonal dominance in the transition matrix confirms that the framework was able to maintain consistent state predictions. The results validate the robustness of the proposed localization framework in environments featuring static tracks, with mean errors ranging from 0.12 m to 0.26 m. The low errors achieved for larger and more prominent static objects highlight the effectiveness of the framework in structured environments. Meanwhile, the moderate errors for smaller or more complex objects, such as trees and narrow poles, suggest potential areas for further improvement in handling variability and limited interaction zones. Additionally, the results emphasize that even without odometry data during testing, the framework can

accurately predict ego vehicle positions using LiDAR-based track observations alone.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we presented a LiDAR-based framework for localizing AV by using classified static tracks as reliable landmarks. With the integration of GNG vocabularies and interaction dictionaries with the MJPF, accurate ego vehicle trajectory predictions were achieved using LiDAR testing dataset without the use of odometry or GPS. It was demonstrated through experimental results that static tracks such as buildings, poles, and trees provided robust reference points, with low mean errors, which validated the effectiveness of the proposed approach. Our future work will focus on incorporating all interaction dictionaries into a unified framework to tackle more complex scenarios. As part of this study, we intend to investigate how the MJPF localizes an ego vehicle in challenging conditions, such as when multiple static tracks appear simultaneously or when observation data is temporarily unavailable. In particular, we plan to explore how the MJPF can be adjusted to these scenarios by leveraging the temporal and spatial relationships captured in the combined dictionaries to refine position predictions for the ego vehicle. By enhancing the framework, we will gain an understanding of the framework's ability to handle sparse and ambiguous observations while maintaining the accuracy of localization. Additionally, the approach can benefit from enhanced theoretical analysis to strengthen its foundational basis. Validation across diverse environments such as tunnels,

highways, and intersections would improve generalizability. Comparative evaluation with established LiDAR localization methods, including Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) techniques like LIO-SAM, Iterative Closest Point (ICP)-based methods, and deep learning-based approaches such as PointNet, is also planned. Furthermore, analyzing computational efficiency and addressing challenges posed by dynamic objects will be essential for real-time deployment.

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